

Effects of two potent biocontrol agents on water hyacinth

R. Praveena and A. Naseema, Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, Vellayani, Thiruvananthapuram 695522, Kerala, India

Water hyacinth [*Eichhornia crassipes* (Mart.) Solms] is a noxious aquatic weed in rice fields. Farmers are compelled to erect barricades to prevent these weeds from entering their fields through irrigation canals. Mechanical removal and chemical methods are advocated, but, for one reason or another, none of the methods proved successful in controlling the weed. In recent years, biological control has received great attention.

Bowers (1986) described a procedure for field application of Collego, a water-suspendible dried spore preparation of the fungus *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* f. sp. *aeschynomene* for the control of Northern jointvetch in rice and soybean fields. Abbot Laboratories-USA developed an experimental formulation of *Cercospora rodmanii* (named ABG-5003) against *E. crassipes* (Te Beest 1991).

A survey was carried out from Feb 2000 to Feb 2001 at quarterly intervals in rice fields of Kerala State, India, to identify fungal pathogens of water hyacinth with biocontrol potential. A number of fungi were isolated from plant parts showing disease symptoms. Pathogenicity tests revealed that seven out of 14 fungi were pathogenic to the weed plant: *Fusarium pallidroseum*, *Myrothecium advena*, *F. oxysporum*, *F. moniliforme*, *Alternaria eichhorniae*, *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, and *Curvularia* sp. Of these pathogenic fungi, *F.*

pallidroseum and *M. advena* caused the drying up of water hyacinth plants. The other pathogenic isolates induced necrosis of leaf tissues around the site of inoculation, spreading 3–5 mm from the wound.

An experiment was conducted to test the host susceptibility of two efficient pathogenic fungi—*F. pallidroseum* and *M. advena*—on 53 cultivated plants and 55 commonly occurring weeds under glasshouse conditions. Ten-day-old *F. pallidroseum* culture grown on rice bran (Thara and Naseema 1998) was used to artificially inoculate leaves and stems of host plants. In the case of *M. advena*, the fungus was grown in Czapek's broth. After 10 d, the broth was shaken and the spore suspension thus obtained was sprayed on the host plants using an atomizer. Control plants were also maintained for each host plant.

F. pallidroseum was found to be pathogenic to seven cultivated plants and six weed plants. Even though *F. pallidroseum* was pathogenic to some cultivated plants such as cashew, papaya, banana, sweet potato, amaranthus, and tomato, it produced only small isolated spots at the point of inoculation and it did not spread. In water hyacinth, it caused complete blighting and drying up of the entire plant within 7 d. The fungus was found to be pathogenic to weed plants that are common in rice fields: *Hydrocotyl asiatica*, *Alloteropis*

cimicina, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Brachiaria ramose*, *Commelina benghalensis*, *C. jacobi*, *Eclipta alba*, *Cynodon dactylon*, and *Phyllanthus niruri*. On the other hand, *M. advena* was not pathogenic to any of the cultivated plants tested, whereas it was pathogenic to weeds such as *Marselia marcescens*, *Pistia stratiotes*, and *Limnocharis flava* in rice fields.

Since water hyacinth is a troublesome weed in rice fields, entailing much labor cost, the possibility of using *F. pallidroseum* and *M. advena* as mycoherbicides must be exploited. Aside from being a rice weed, water hyacinth is also a problem in waterways where herbicide cannot be used as the water is used for drinking and other household purposes. Preliminary studies showed no harmful effects of these fungi on aquatic fauna. Our study revealed that *F. pallidroseum* and *M. advena* could be used for biological control of water hyacinth as they are not expected to create problems for plants of economic and ecological importance.

References

- Bowers RC. 1986. Commercialization of Collego™: an industrialist's view. *Weed Sci.* 34 (Suppl.):24-25.
- Thara SS, Naseema A. 1998. Biocontrol of water hyacinth using fungal pathogens. In: Proceedings of the 10th Kerala Science Congress, 1998, Kozhikode, Kerala. p 362-365.
- Te Beest DO. 1991. Microbial control of weeds. New York: Chapman and Hall. 282 p.